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SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF IMPROVING MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY BY EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

The urgency of the above-mentioned problem is due to the necessity of creating a new, modern system of management of educational institutions. This process is based on the provisions of the State National Program "Education" Ukraine of the XXI Century, the national doctrine of the development of Ukraine's education in the 21st century. These provisions state that state policy in the field of education is aimed at strengthening the role of local self-government bodies, increasing the participation of parents, charitable councils, sponsors, public organizations, foundations, etc.

Key words: socio-psychological peculiarities, efficiency of management, educational institution.

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СОЦІАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГІЧНІ ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ПІДВИЩЕННЯ ЕФЕКТИВНОСТІ УПРАВЛІННЯ НАВЧАЛЬНИМИ ЗАКЛАДАМИ

В роботі вказується на необхідності зміні ідеології управління навчальними закладами, побудови нової філософії освіти, яка вимагає від керівника зміни погляду на свою роль і місця в процесі управління, формуванню творчого педагогічного колективу, досягнення високого рівня розвитку кожного його члена, мотивації і стимулювання творчої діяльності суб'єктів управління.

Ключові слова: соціально-психологічні особливості, ефективність управління, навчальний заклад.

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СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ УЧЕБНЫМИ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯМИ

В работе указывается на необходимость изменения идеологии управления учебными заведениями, построения новой философии образования, которая требует от руководителя изменения взгляда на свою роль и место в процессе управления, формирование творческого педагогического коллектива, достижения высокого уровня развития каждого его члена, мотивации и стимулирования творческой деятельности субъектов управления.

Ключевые слова: социально-психологические особенности, эффективность управления, учебное заведение.

The creation of a modern system of management of educational institutions and increasing its effectiveness is one of the most urgent tasks of modernizing the national education. This process is based on the provisions of the State National Program "Education" Ukraine of the XXI Century, the national doctrine of the development of Ukraine's education in the 21st century. These provisions state that state policy in the field of education is aimed at strengthening the role of local self-government bodies, increasing the participation of parents, charitable councils, sponsors, public organizations, foundations, etc.". **Our article is devoted to this current problem.**

Purpose: to reveal modern socio-psychological peculiarities of increasing the effectiveness of management of educational institutions.

Statement of the main material.

Based on the above-mentioned state provisions, it is possible to point out that one of the directions of changes in management activity are:

1. Provision of state-public management. Its main task is to ensure the dialogue of administrative management structures with self-government bodies, individual professional groups or team members in order to ensure a positive result of educational activity.

It provides the involvement of the pedagogical community, parents, public organizations, and the students themselves. On this subject, the development of new management models or the modernization of old ones is necessary. It is important that all components of the model: administrative bodies, the pedagogical community, parent committees, student (self-governing), sponsored organizations and enterprises, other educational institutions, etc. - formed a united management system, each element of which would be inter-related and filled with specific content and linked to other elements. The creation of such structures is a sign of democratization of governance.

Characteristic signs of the restoration and development of the educational institution are a decrease in the share of the individual order, the growth of the scope of coordination activities, the constant regulation of the ties, interaction of subjects of management of development.

Participation in management unites people around solving of common goals, engage them in joint activities, increases the interest in the development of the educational institution, contributes to the effectiveness of the reform of education.

2. Change in the ideology of management. It should be based on the human centered philosophy of modern management, the principles of humanization, the idea of cooperation, the rejection of dictate at all levels.

The main emphasis of managerial activity should be directed to the motives, values, interests of people, to the formation of the mechanism of human relations, the main values of which are: the value of intellect, morality, aes-

thetics of relations, the value of self-determination, democracy, the value of creativity, active principles, the value of interactions, etc.

The instruments for implementing the human centered approach in management are: respect and trust in people, which generate success.

The principle of respect and trust in a person puts forward specific requirements for the leader. According to Yu.A. Konarzhevsky [4, 46-471], the principle of respect and trust to the person puts forward specific requirements for the leader:

- respect for the personal dignity of a human, his character and abilities;
- respect and preservation of man in himself and others;
- providing the person with freedom of choice;
- trust in a person, belief in its inexhaustible potential;
- Creation of an atmosphere of trust based on mutual respect;
- manifestation of high demands on the person on the basis of respect for her;
- creating an environment in which he can manifest himself, to reveal his capabilities;
- maximum development of initiative, creativity, ability to find oneself in the team;
- encouragement of achievements and personal contribution of everyone to the work of the educational institution;
- providing each teacher and student with personal security in the team.

The "new philosophy" of education requires the leader to change his view of his role and place in the management process. The leader is "a social architect, uniting the will of individual teachers in the collective pedagogical will of the team. It is the leader who constructs his target integrity, the person who creates the conditions for the development of the initiative of each educator, his creative potential. This is a social engineer who projects and embodies the relations of cooperation between people, takes each teacher out of the grip of inertia, triggers a powerful motor of pedagogical creativity. It is the essence of management, oriented to person" [1]

Crucial in it will be not only his knowledge and skills in the management of educational institutions as a social and pedagogical system, but also his emergence as a leader-manager. This is due to the growth of the influence of the leader's personality, the departure from traditional hierarchical relations (chief-subordinate), ability to influence subordinates due to his image, high rating in the team.

3. The formation of a creative pedagogical team, the achievement of a high level of development of each of its members.

The success of the work of an educational institution largely depends on how much each teacher understands and accepts the overall goals and objec-

tives of the team, seeks to implement them, revealing their creative potential. The creative activity of the teacher is associated with the search for non-standard ways of solving complex pedagogical problems. Therefore, pedagogical creativity is a process of constant search and introduction of new pedagogical ideas and technologies aimed at ensuring the development and self-development of the personality.

The main circumstances for creating a creative team according to L.M. Karamushka [3] and L.E. Orban [8] are favorable psychological climate, which is defined as a qualitative aspect of interpersonal relations, which contribute to or interfere the productive cooperative activity of members of the collective.

The formation of the psychological climate is related to the nature of business and interpersonal relations between the members of the collective and the leader, the content of the work activity and the form of its organization; the personality of the leader and the style of leadership of the team, the individual psychological and age characteristics of each employee.

Selection and proper placement of personnel in accordance with their abilities and capabilities. Therefore, it is so important to study and to know your employees, to formulate goals and to involve in achieving them on the basis of taking into account the interests of the subordinate.

The selection and proper placement of staff is associated with an assessment of the possibility of development and creative achievements of each educator. At the same time, it is important for the leader to support valuable initiatives, promising ideas, and their expert evaluation, which will help improve the work of the organization.

Motivation and stimulation of the creative activity of teachers. The development of an educational institution can be ensured by the creation of all conditions and real opportunities for the development of creative initiative and professional abilities of educators. In creating an atmosphere of friendly collective cooperation underlie the whole essence of administrative work. This is the main activity of the work day of the administration. This is a great and subtle art of combining acknowledged by everybody business and moral authority of the administration with the initiative of the staff of the institution.

The positive motivation of employees is ensured if:

- results expected by the manager were clearly defined and known to every educator;
- rewards for achieving high results were known to everybody;
- rewards should be valuable to the performers;
- status of the teacher in the team and the attitude towards him from colleagues depended on how he works;

- control system provided an objective evaluation of the results of work, and every educator was sure of it;

- results of each educator were known in the team;

- rewards received corresponded to the results of the work, and the educators did not doubt the fairness of the rewards [2].

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Let's turn to some tips for creating conditions for the creative work of the team:

- take the responsibility for creation of organizational climate where creativity and an initiative would be encouraged;

- be inventive. Always look for new forms of work organization that seek to maximize creative interaction;

- try to identify and get rid of those norms and procedures that stifle and limit the initiative of subordinates;

- create an organizational mechanism for the development and implementation of ideas for innovation;

- formulate new tasks understandably and visually, paying attention mainly to those that require creativity;

- make incentives for creative initiative a part of your overall management policy;

- give workers more freedom and independence in their own work, do not engage in petty tutelage;

- remember that the creative atmosphere does not appear by itself. It is necessary to prepare the appropriate soil for it [2, 3].

Creation and development of such an advanced training system which would stimulate the emergence of need of professional self-development and creative growth. Here, both group and individual forms of work with educators are important. The activity of moderators which function is to reveal hidden opportunities and unrealized skills and to help a specialist who studies is gaining popularity.

Currently, a new technology is being tested for the development of professionalism and personal growth of teaching staff - scientific and methodological support. It can be represented as a process of continuous professional interaction of subjects in search, substantiation, practical implementation, approbation of new approaches in solving problems of educational practice [15].

4. The direction of management of the educational institution for the implementation of its health-saving and health-forming functions.

This activity must be carried out based on the definition of health, which is fixed in the statute of the World Health Organization of the UN General Assembly: "Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being of a person, and not only the absence of disease and physical defects." In other words, health should be considered as a state of dynamic equilibrium between the body and the environment at the biological, psychological and social levels.

WHO experts identified four groups of factors affecting the health of adolescents and young people:

- individual propensity to disrupt health (heredity, developmental peculiarities in the prenatal period, accidents or diseases in the past, character of education in childhood, etc.);

- a social predisposition to the violation of health (the value orientation of society, the social image of a person, the individual way of life, the characteristics of behavior characteristic of a certain group, education in adolescence, etc.);

- the circumstances of the child's life that have developed to adolescence (income, style of family life, living condition, the opportunity to get a job, stress and crisis situations, etc.)

- the available opportunities for maintaining health (availability of free access to health services, the nature of nutrition, sanitation, education in the field of health preservation and promotion, access to alcohol, tobacco and drugs, etc.) [5; 6].

The main conclusion reached by the experts is: "In such orderly environments as school, there are ample opportunities for taking the necessary measures without going beyond the activities inherent in these institutions. However, these measures should be based on a system of psychological and social support, the emphasis should be on the self-organization of young people in accordance with their needs and interests "[17].

Therefore, health care should not be reduced to introducing new, specialized subjects into the training program. The problem of preserving and strengthening health "requires the restructuring of the entire educational activity of the educational institution in order to achieve compliance with medical

norms (health in a narrow sense), on the one hand, and public demand (health in a broad sense), on the other" [9].

In this regard, health-forming activities in the education process should be conducted in three interrelated directions: pedagogical, physiological-valeological and psychological.

The pedagogical direction includes: reasonable taking into account the existing realities of the valeologization of school culture (valeologization of organizational, pedagogical, social, sanitary, hygienic, aesthetic, spatial and tempo-rhythmical conditions reflecting the typical rhythm of school life, the pace of its life and the amount of workload in the work of teachers and students); the change in the educational policy of the school (the transition to a broad differentiation of the learning process in order to provide broad opportunities for individual education of all schoolchildren in the context of joint educational activities, taking into account the valeological requirements for the organization of lessons, organization of systemic valeological education at all levels of school education), organization of children's self-government and the introduction of socialization programs of schoolchildren and prevention of the risk of social disadaptation with the involvement of social educator.

The psychological direction assumes, first of all, the creation of a special psychological service; firstly, it would conduct development work with all schoolchildren in all its forms, and also provide psychological counseling and support to families of children, psychological support of the educational process; secondly, it could provide holistic assistance to children at risk; and, thirdly, the humanization of the psychological microclimate of the educational institution at all levels.

Medical (physiological-valeological) direction assumes: maintenance of hygienic conditions of educational process; organization of extensive educational work among students and their parents, as well as educators; systemic rehabilitation work in relation to all participants of the educational process.

5. Enrichment and development of management functions of educational systems.

At the heart of the management of educational institutions are various types of activities, operations, actions of subjects of management, called management functions. The most often used classification is proposed by Yu.A. Konarzhevsky [4]. He distinguishes: analysis, goal-setting and planning, organization, control, regulation and correction.

Reforming of education in Ukraine led to the development of managerial functions of the head of the educational institution, which is associated with quantitative and qualitative changes occurring both in education and in society as a whole.

Quantitative changes are carried out under the influence of internal factors of the rethinking of each function in the conditions of democratization of management, and consequently, the degree of its centralization and decentralization, the optimal combination of governance and self-government; in the conditions of changing or choosing the profile of an educational institution, etc.

Qualitative changes are carried out under the influence of changes in the external environment, the formation of a new internal and foreign policy of the state, sets new goals and tasks for educational institutions.

In these conditions, new approaches to the implementation of the management functions of the educational institution are needed, its renewal. We distinguish the modernized management functions, which most correspond to the requirements of the development of the educational institution in connection with the change in the environment. Those are: prognostic, advisory, representative, politico-diplomatic and managerial.

The prognostic function reflects the vision of the development prospects of an educational institution in connection with changes in the environment, forecasting the results of its activities. The advisory function which has arisen in the conditions of need of self-government and self-organization of pedagogical systems also includes the qualified help (councils) of the head to pedagogical collective and public on various questions of educational activity with involvement to it of specialists of various branches. The need to present the educational institution at different levels, to establish its diverse contacts, has led to the appearance of a representative function. Comprehension and reflection in its activities of the domestic and foreign policies of the state, national revival and national culture has found reflection in political and diplomatic function. The managerial function strengthens attention to the leadership of the pedagogical team, the use of situational management and motivational methods.

Nowadays, researchers of management problems combine two functions into one, which indicates the dual purpose of such a function and the logical relationship between actions aimed at achieving both one and the other goal. In this regard, we can distinguish functions: goal-setting and forecasting, planning and programming, organization and motivation, control and regulation. R. Glaser [12; 13] and D. Olson [14], classifying control functions, also distinguish double functions: design-analytical, motivation-target, planned-prognostic, organizational-performing, control-diagnostic, regulatory-corrective and indicate on their interconnection and interaction.

Practice of managerial activity imply that highlighted traditional functions (analysis, goal-setting and planning, organization, control, coordination and regulation) remain leading.

Each of these functions requires its own specific information, both internal and external. Therefore, an important condition for improving the management of educational institutions is, on the one hand, providing information support for the adoption of managerial decisions, and on the other hand, the growth of information factors in the dissemination of new ideas for the development of the educational institution and management technologies. Information "nourishes" the function of analysis and it is not without reason that it is called "bread of management".

Enrichment and development of the function of analysis in modern conditions is associated not only with the need for a deep analysis of the internal factors of the educational institution, but also analysis of changes in the external environment and its impact on the quality of educational processes. This will facilitate the implementation of a comprehensive assessment of the situation and forecasting the development of the educational institution. An analysis aimed at revealing not only shortcomings but also ways of using available reserves requires the definition of the role of each member of the team in solving the problems of the development of educational institution, reflective thinking and introspection.

The initial position in the development of the forecasting and planning function is the use of the possibilities of a scientific approach: reliance on the principles of management (scientific, analytical substantiation, purposefulness, reality, continuity, concreteness) strengthening the perspective direction of planning, implementing targeted strategic planning, provides ways to achieve the goals of the end result through a solution system of tasks (ways of achieving the goal); holistic combination of promising, yearly and operational plans as an integrated system; mastering the technology of goal-setting, the use of positions of goal-setting in management.

The renewal of the organizational function is associated with the creation of conditions for the development of a management structure where the functions would be clearly distributed and the principles of subordination and coordination would be optimally combined. This combination of vertical, horizontal control and self-management by establishing the optimal ratio of external control and self-organization of the controlled system [4].

It is also necessary to update the organizational forms of scientific and methodological work that contribute to the most effective solution of the tasks.

The most important component of effective management is the formation of the organizational culture of the educational institution, in which E.A. Smirnov [9] understands the system of socially progressive formal and informal rules and norms of activity, customs and traditions, individual and group interests, characteristics of the behavior of personnel in this organiza-

tional structure, management style, indicators of employee satisfaction with working conditions, level of cooperation and employee compatibility among themselves and with organization, development prospects.

In conditions of democratization of management, the view on the functions of control, regulation and correction of educational processes is changing. Its renewal is associated with the growth of the psychological foundations of control, a person-centred approach in management, restructuring it on the basis of the development of the creative forces of human, confidence in him. It, first of all, demands strengthening the motivational basis of control, an optimal combination of control and self-control. Self-evaluation of the work provides an opportunity to take corrective measures in time.

Modern studies show that in educational institutions it is necessary to create a unified system of internal control, certification and professional development of teachers, is a triune basis for working with personnel. With this approach, managerial stereotypes change: now control and certification can not be considered separately from the system of their continuous professional education – outside of university training, outside of scientific and methodological training in an educational institution and outside the system of professional development. This is due to the fact that the professional competence of the teacher grows and is evaluated in the course of control and certification, is formed when getting an education in the institute and in the system of professional development.

Monitoring is important in control activities. It allows to identify the results of the educational process, the nature of the deviations from the planned, it allows to respond in a timely manner to what is happening and make adjustments to the educational process. Monitoring activity is the most important direction in updating modern management of educational institutions.

Educational results can act as objects of internal and external evaluation.

Subjects of external evaluation, taking into account the conditions of a general educational institution, can be: state structures, among whose functions - control of educational results; educational institutions of professional education; independent experts involved in the evaluation of educational outcomes by the educational institutions themselves; parents, graduates of educational institutions.

Modernization of education management involves the rejection of exclusively departmental evaluation of educational results and the transition to a state-public assessment system. It is also about abandoning a departmental evaluation based on the judgments of management personnel and moving to an assessment based on expert opinions.

6. Implementation of a strategic approach to management.

The concept of "strategic management" was introduced by I. Ansoff in the late 1970s. With this concept he defined "an interconnected complex of planning the strategy of organization and implementation of the developed plans for life" [10].

Strategic management involves an answer to three critical questions: in what position is the organization (institution) currently located? in what position would it like to be in 3, 5, 10 years?; how to achieve the desired position?

To answer the first question, managers have to understand the current situation well, information is for this purpose necessary, that is, relevant data for analyzing past, present and future situations; the second question reflects the orientation of strategic management for the future. The third issue is related to the implementation of the chosen strategy, during which the two previous stages can be adjusted.

Strategic management is a cyclical process based on a permanent study of the external and internal environment of the educational institution, that is, a strategic diagnosis of the internal and external conditions that make it possible to form a clear picture of the strengths and weaknesses of the institution, as well as the opportunities and threats that exist for it in the external environment. The first is necessary for a critical assessment of the capacity of the institution, to identify the real level of claims in the planning of activities. The second allows us to identify and either positive external factors, obstacles that prevent their achievement.

The result of the analysis is the mission of the educational institution - purpose, commitment, suggestion of what the institution was created for. The main provisions of the mission are specified in the spheres of activity, considered as strategic for the success of the educational institution. These are so-called policies or strategic priorities for the activities of specified areas.

Mission and policy (strategic priorities) is the main for the development of a strategic plan – plans of the activities of the educational institution, are seamlessly combined among themselves and represent an integral system.

With the adoption of the plan, the next phase of the strategic management process begins – the implementation of the strategy, accompanied by appropriate structural and budgetary changes, redistribution of resources along the areas and bringing the structure in line with the tasks to be accomplished.

The final phase of the management cycle is the evaluation of the achieved, the results, the process based on the creation of a system for monitoring its parameters, characterized by a number of indicators, the monitoring of which provides the opportunity to control the process. On the basis of monitoring conclusions if necessary the mission is specified, plans are corrected, changes are made to structure and the budgetary procedures.

As for the instructors themselves, an extremely important problem is the development of new criteria for evaluating their results. The new criteria should take into account not only what knowledge the student has mastered, but also how his activities are organized (how he practices the teaching material, how he selects and shapes the methods of teaching, etc.)

Based on the above, it can be concluded that the search of ways to improve the management of educational institutions is one of the large and complex tasks of modernizing current education. Modernization of management activities requires new approaches to management in both form and content. One of the conditions of its implementation is a systematic approach, as well as the desire of managers to implement modern achievements of science and advanced practices in management activities.

Prospects of further researches are in development of universal models of implementation in educational process of innovative managerial technologies which would take into account both psychological, and social factors. It is also necessary to find out the psychological basis of preparation of students of pedagogical universities for the implementation of managerial activities in school and other.

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